

INCLUSIVE EDUCATION AND OPPORTUNITIES FOR STUDENTS WITH DISABILITIES

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Annotation: This article discusses the introduction of inclusive education, mainly in urban areas, as well as the fact that in rural areas children with special needs are still excluded from education, and opportunities for people with disabilities have been created.

Key words: inclusive education, expert, Oliy Majlis, scientific education, health, pupil, student, opportunity.

The most important factor determining the development of mankind in its development is social equality, social justice. The basic reality that reflects these aspects is that the conditions created for people with disabilities in society allow them to live freely and freely in the environment in which they live.

Today in our country there are ample opportunities for people with disabilities to get a profession and education.

In particular, as noted in the "Concept for the Development of Inclusive Education in Public Education for 2020-2025", approved by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on October 13, 2020 No. PP-4860, today in the field of physical or mental development of the country in total, in 86 specialized schools and schools - 21.2 thousand students study in boarding schools for children with disabilities (hereinafter referred to as specialized educational institutions), 6.1 thousand students study in 21 sanatorium-type boarding schools. In addition, 13.3 thousand schoolchildren in need of long-term treatment will be trained individually at home.

In 2014-2016, in cooperation with the European Union, the project "Inclusive Education for Children with Special Educational Needs in Uzbekistan" was implemented. In the project's boundaries:

pilot sites were created in 5 regions of the country;

More than 150 medical-psychological-pedagogical commissions and more than 1,300 teachers have been trained on inclusive education services;

The curricula of educational organizations for retraining and advanced training of teaching staff include 3 training modules on the introduction of inclusive practices in the education system;

Inclusive education services were provided to more than 2,000 children with special educational needs and their parents;

In Tashkent, Samarkand, Namangan, Khorezm and Surkhandarya regions, 5 experimental resource centers and 15 experimental schools have been created, in which more than 800 children study.

A number of legal acts on the introduction of inclusive education have been adopted.

These documents provide for social support for children in need of special assistance, upbringing, which is part of our society, their opportunity to be among healthy children and show their abilities and potential, measures for spiritual development are determined. September 2018, No. PP-3931 "On measures to introduce new management principles in the public education system" noted specific tasks to create an adaptive environment that will further expand their access to education (including inclusive education).

The goal of inclusive education is to provide quality education to all children, regardless of their abilities and status. At the same time, the principle of inclusiveness suggests that children with disabilities should live in a family and study in a regular school with their peers in order to have a positive mental and social development. The inclusive education system allows a child in a wheelchair to attend any nearby school, receive special assistance in learning to read and write if he has learning difficulties, and a child who does not attend classes is guaranteed appropriate assistance. back to school. Over the past two decades, significant work has been done to educate children with special needs in the general education system. However, the introduction of inclusive education takes place mainly at the urban level, and in rural areas, children with special needs are still excluded from education, or parents in rural areas face difficulties in ensuring that their children with disabilities attend special institutions in urban areas. Therefore, the inclusion of children with special needs in inclusive education should ensure that all children with special needs in all regions are covered.

Children with disabilities should not only be treated as disabled, but they should also be treated holistically. This requires planning education for children with special needs, taking into account the needs that may arise throughout his or her life. In addition, inclusive education requires the elimination of shortcomings existing in children with disabilities, correction, compensation, as well as the acquisition of knowledge and skills, parallel professional training. At the heart of this principle is an early approach to children with special needs at an early age. The education of children with special needs should not end with their primary and secondary special education. It also requires vocational and higher

education for children with disabilities. After all, one of the tasks of the inclusive education system is the comprehensive development of children with special needs, ensuring all their rights.

Increasingly, in their practice, teachers of preschool and school educational institutions are faced with a child, since some of his features do not stand out from their peers in society. As a rule, it is difficult for these children to gradually assimilate the curriculum in the classroom and in the classroom. Not so long ago, the definition of “children with disabilities” was added to the pedagogical dictionary, but today this is a one-time problem that has become a problem of teaching and raising children.

Higher education in Uzbekistan still exists for a select disadvantaged stratum capable of withstanding fierce competition in entrance exams. This situation persists due to the small number of higher education institutions and the high demand for higher education, with 60% of Uzbekistan's population under 30 years of age. Last year, applications were announced for 60 national universities of Uzbekistan and their 19 branches. At the same time, the government approved a quota of 80,965 students.

This year, an average of 8 people applied for one student place, and in some provinces the competition was more than 20 people for 1 place. For example, the Tashkent Medical Academy last year set a record - 23.2 applicants per place.

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On measures to radically improve the system of state support for persons with disabilities”, adopted on December 1, 2017, provides for benefits for persons with disabilities when passing the entrance exam to higher educational institutions. proceeds from the principle of creating equal conditions for all and applies the measure of positive discrimination, i.e. provides special benefits to the stratum with disabilities, racial and gender factors.

List of links:

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